

UK Project Report

The Formation of Children's Values in School: A Study on Value Development Among Primary School Children in Switzerland and the United Kingdom

September 2022 - August 2022

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Imprint:

Royal Holloway, University of London

Egham Hill, Egham TW20 0EX

United Kingdom

Project Report for the Research project: VALISE - The Formation of Children's Values in School: A Study on Value Development among Primary School Children in Switzerland and the United Kingdom

SNSF project number: 100019M_189365

Duration of Project: September 2020 – August 2024

German Title: Eine Studie der Werteentwicklung von Primarschulkindern in der Schweiz und in Grossbritannien

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September, 2022

Table of Contents

List of Tables and Figures	4
List of Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Results of UK data collection.....	7
2.1 Recruitment of schools.....	7
2.2 Descriptive statistics of the sample	8
2.2.1 Sample of pupils.....	8
2.2.2 Sample of teachers.....	10
3. Theoretical and methodical anchoring.....	11
4. Selection of initial analyses.....	16
4.1 Value structure in primary children.....	16
4.2 Values priorities of primary children.....	18
4.3 Structure of teachers' value-related educational goals.....	21
4.4 Priorities of teachers' value-related educational goals.....	22
5. A qualitative study on how values are instilled in primary school.....	23
6. Follow-up and thank you	25
7. Research Output	25
References.....	26

List of Tables and Figures

Table 1 Sample size and sex of pupils	8
Table 2 Age of pupils	8
Table 3 Country of birth	9
Table 4 Languages spoken at home	9
Table 5 Sample size and sex of teachers	10
Table 6 Age of teachers	10
Table 7 Country of birth	10
Table 8 Years of experience	10
Table 9 List and abbreviations of higher order values and their corresponding value types	12
Table 10 List and abbreviation/variable name of value-related educational goals	14
Table 11 Value priorities subsumed to value type; by year group (Year 2 and Year 3)	19
Table 12 Value priorities subsumed to higher order value; by year group (Year 2 and Year 3)	20
Table 13 Value-related educational goals - subsumed to value type; combined (female/male and Year 2 / Year 3)	22
Table 14 Value-related educational goals subsumed to higher order value; combined (female/male male and Year 2 / Year 3)	23
Figure 1 Schwartz's structure of values (1992), own adaptation	12
Figure 2 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (Year 2)	17
Figure 3 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (Year 3)	18
Figure 4 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS	21

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
KS1	Key stage 1
KS2	Key stage 2
M	Mean
MDS	Multidimensional scaling
N	Sample size
PBVS-C	Picture-Based Value Survey for Children
PVQ	Portrait Value Questionnaire
SD	Standard deviation

1. Introduction

The Valise project will illuminate how primary schools shape children's personal value development, by employing a longitudinal design in Switzerland along with a comparative cross-sectional study in the UK. It will set the foundations for theory building on formation of values in the school context. This knowledge is essential for providing evidence-based guidance for values education in schools. This project report is based on the Swiss project report (Scholz-Kuhn, R. & Oeschger, T., 2022a) and technical report (Scholz-Kuhn, R. & Oeschger, T., 2022b). It focuses on the cross-sectional UK data of the Valise project.

The report details the recruitment process in the UK as well as documenting selected results of the data collection, particularly how the realised samples of the pupils as well as the teachers are structured. In addition, a selection of initial analyses will be presented providing a first insight into the research topics of the study. It should be emphasised once again that these are only individual results.

In the third part, the results of a qualitative study (Jones, 2022) on how teachers instil values in the primary school setting will be discussed. Emma Jones of the UK research team conducted this qualitative study on how values are taught in primary schools as part of her Master's degree. Using semi-structured interviews, the aim of this research was to allow primary school teachers to speak freely about their personal experiences of teaching and implanting values to their students. The following two main research questions were investigated: 1) What are the values that are important to the teachers and how do they transmit these to their pupils? And 2) What methods and contexts are used by the teachers to instil values (both implicitly and explicitly, and through formal academic lessons and more informal times of the school day), and what is the role of the wider school community (including the school ethos and the Head Teacher)? Both deductive qualitative content analysis as well as an inductive approach using thematic analysis were applied.

If you are interested in more detailed results, please feel free to contact the Valise team (Twitter @VALISEproject or <https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-formation-in-school/>).

2. Results of UK data collection

2.1 Recruitment of schools

The project team planned to recruit pupils from UK primary schools and their teachers in the first phase of the project (period September 2020 - May 2021). The aim was to recruit a total of approx. 500 children in Year 2 of the UK school system (around 6-7 years old). This year group was chosen to match the Swiss students at time one. Over 200 schools have been contacted in this period, but due to the Covid-19 situation in the UK and school restrictions, all schools declined the invitation.

A year later, after the Covid-19 situation has noticeably improved, recruitment in the UK has resumed. Year 2 as well as Year 3 classes and teachers and assistants were invited to maximise the success of the data collection. Furthermore, it was part of a comprehensive values-related lesson offered to the schools. Former primary teachers from the research team not only administered the values-related questionnaire, but also encouraged pupils to further deepen their understanding of their values in carefully designed values-related activities. These activities were constructed to match the PSHE (personal, social, health and economic education standards) taught in UK primary schools to enrich the study and promote positive replies from the invited schools.

First, the school headmasters were contacted via email detailing the study and PSHE activities in a flyer and letter containing all relevant information. In total, 501 schools in the counties Berkshire, Surrey, Greater London, Essex, Stoke-on-Trent and Leicester were invited at this point alone. Eleven schools from South England areas (Berkshire, Surrey, Greater London and Essex) accepted the invitation to take part in the Valise project, totalling 37 classes (22 Year 2 classes and 15 Year 3 classes) with an average of 25-30 pupils per class. Only about 50% of parents gave their consent for their child to participate in the study. Of those 574 pupils, 26 were absent due to illness, appointment or quarantine, and 10 pupils did not want to take part in the study.

2.2 Descriptive statistics of the sample

This cross-sectional study was part of the larger Valise study. The following statistics and models only comprise of the UK sample.

Five-hundred and thirty-eight typically developing primary children in Year 2 and Year 3 were recruited from South England areas (Berkshire, Surrey, Greater London and Essex). The following section is divided in two parts. The first section focuses on the sample of the pupils (see 2.1.1), including a presentation of the sample size and sex of the pupils (table 1), information about their mean age (table 2), the country of birth (table 3) and the languages that are spoken at home (table 4). The second section describes the sample of the teachers (see 2.1.2), including the sample size and sex of the teachers (table 5), the age of the teachers (table 6), the country of birth (table 7) and the years of experience (table 8).

2.1.1 Sample of pupils

Table 1 *Sample size and sex of pupils*

	Combined		Year 2		Year 3	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Girl	270	50.20	166	53.55	99	43.42
Boy	266	49.40	139	44.84	125	54.82
Missing	2	.40	5	1.61	4	1.76
Total	538	100.0	310	100.00	228	100.00

Table 2 *Age of pupils*

	Combined		Year 2		Year 3	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Girls	7.13	.67	6.77	.45	7.75	.48
Boys	7.29	.67	6.84	.51	7.79	.43
Total	7.21	.67	6.80	.48	7.77	.45

Table 3 *Country of birth (Year 2 and Year 3 combined)*

Country of birth	N	%
United Kingdom	371	69.00
other country	115	21.40
don't know	44	8.20
Missing	8	1.50
Total	538	100.00

Country of birth specified

The children were asked to specify their country of birth if known. Most children who were not born in the UK were born in Asia ($n_{\text{total}} = 47$; China $n = 18$ [11 from Hong Kong], India $n = 17$, Pakistan $n = 4$ to name the most frequent). Second was Europe with 24 children (most frequent were Romania and Italy with each 4 children, followed by Germany, Hungary, Ireland and Switzerland with each 2 children). Fourteen children were born in Africa (most frequent were South Africa [$n = 3$] and Dubai [$n = 2$]), 9 children were born in North America (USA $n = 7$ and Canada $n = 2$) and one in South America (Brazil). Six children were born in Australia and 7 answers were illegible or not a known country or city.

Table 4 *Languages spoken at home (Year 2 and Year 3 combined)*

Languages spoken at home	N	%
English	267	49.60
English and another language	223	41.40
Another Language	46	8.60
Missing	2	.40
Total	538	100.00

2.1.2 Sample of teachers

Table 5 *Sample size and sex of teachers*

Sex	N	%
Female	27	71.10
Male	4	10.5
Missing	7	18.40
Total	38	100.00

Table 6 *Age of teachers*

	M	SD
Female	41.70	13.62
Male	36.25	12.69
Total	41.68	12.84

Table 7 *Country of birth*

Country of birth	N	%
United Kingdom	33	86.80
Ireland	1	2.60
Poland	1	2.60
Portugal	1	2.60
Zimbabwe	1	2.60
Total	38	100.00

Table 8 *Years of experience*

	Years of Experience		
	N	M	SD
Female	27	12.33	9.14
Male	4	4.00	.82
Total	37	11.00	8.64

3. Theoretical and methodical anchoring

How are values defined and how can they be organized?

Values express what is important to an individual important in life and what they strive for. They are at the centre of a person's self-concept and identity of a person (Hitlin & Piliavin 2004). Values are not only as fundamental abstract beliefs, but they are also inextricably linked to motivation and orientations and thus guide our actions (Bardi & Schwartz, 2003). In both adults and children, values are considered to be relatively stable over time and are therefore regarded as guidelines in the life course of an individual (Schwartz, 1992).

A comprehensively established model on personal value orientations (value priorities and value structures) comes from the theory of human values by Shalom Schwartz (1992). Basic values in this model are organised in a circular structure and include the following ten basic values: universalism, benevolence, tradition, conformity, security, power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation and self-direction (figure 1, table 9). Moreover, Schwartz (1992, 1994, 2012) summarised these ten basic values along their motivational goals into a circular structure resulting in four higher-order value types. These include self-transcendence (universalism, benevolence), conservation (tradition, conformity, security), self-enhancement (power and achievement) and openness to change (hedonism, stimulation, self-direction).

Values lying next to each other in the circle show similarities in terms of their motivational focus and are mutually supporting. In the case of the basic values universalism and benevolence, for example, both on fellow human beings and their needs are central, whereas the core values of achievement and power centre around the individual and his or her own needs.

Figure 1

Schwartz's structure of values (1992), own adaptation

Table 9 List and abbreviations of higher order values and their corresponding value types

Higher order value	Abbreviation/ name of item	Value type	Abbreviation/ name of item	Example item
Self-transcendence	SeTr	Universalism	UN	to make new friends
		Benevolence	BE	to help others
		Tradition	TR	to think of God
Conservation	Cons	Conservation	CO	to follow the rules
		Security	SE	to be safe
Self-enhancement	SeEn	Power	PO	to be rich and powerful
		Achievement	AC	to be the best
Openness to change	OtC	Hedonism	HE	to enjoy life
		Stimulation	ST	to do exciting things

How can we measure children's values?

The value priorities and the value structures of the pupils were measured by the Picture-Based Value Survey for Children (PBVS-C, Döring et al. 2010). For this purpose, 20 pictures were presented, in each of which a gender-neutral main figure performs a value-relevant action to facilitate an easy identification for the children with the main character. The children assessed how important the values depicted in the picture are and arranged these in a given hierarchical answer format (important pictures at the top, unimportant at the bottom). For the basic value of benevolence, the main character helps a child to get up after a bicycle accident. The core value power is illustrated by the main character sitting on a throne appearing rich and powerful. A picture in which the main character is lying on a hammock in the sun and enjoys life represents the basic value of hedonism. A picture with the main character on a bicycle and a policeman putting a helmet on the child shows the basic value security ("being safe") (see figure 1 or table 1 for examples).

How can we measure teacher's value-related educational goals?

The focus of this study was not on the teachers' personal values, but on their value-related educational goals. These are defined as the values that the teachers want to promote in their class. Teachers completed an online questionnaire on their value-related educational goals, using the well-established Portrait Values Questionnaire (PVQ-21, Schwartz et al., 2001). The PVQ-21 consists of 21 items that include a short verbal portrait describing a person's life goals or aspirations. With the use of a 6-point Likert scale, the teachers rated how much they want their students to resemble the person described in each item. In the process, it is ascertained how similar their students should be to the 21 value-oriented person descriptions. Several items represent each of the 10 basic values as defined by Schwartz (see table 12).

Table 12 List and abbreviation/variable name of value-related educational goals

Value	Variable	Item
Universalism	PVQ_UN1	They think it is important that every person in the world be treated equally. They believe everyone should have equal opportunities in life.
	PVQ_UN2	It is important to them to listen to people who are different from them. Even when they disagree with them, they still want to understand them.
	PVQ_UN3	They strongly believe that people should care for nature. Looking after the environment is important to them.
Benevolence	PVQ_BE1	It's very important to them to help the people around them. They want to care for their well-being.
	PVQ_BE2	It is important to them to be loyal to their friends. They want to devote themselves to people close to them.
Tradition	PVQ_TR1	It is important to them to be humble and modest. They try not to draw attention to themselves.
	PVQ_TR2	Tradition is important to them. They try to follow the customs handed down by their religion or their family.
Conservation	PVQ_CO1	They believe that people should do what they're told. They think people should follow rules at all times, even when no-one is watching.
	PVQ_CO2	It is important to them always to behave properly. They want to avoid doing anything people would say is wrong.
Security	PVQ_SE1	It is important to them to live in secure surroundings. They avoid anything that might endanger their safety.
	PVQ_SE2	It is important to them that the government ensures their safety against all threats. They want the state to be strong so it can defend its citizens.
Power	PVQ_PO1	It is important to them to be rich. They want to have a lot of money and expensive things.
	PVQ_PO2	It is important to them to get respect from others. They want people to do what they say.
Achievement	PVQ_AC1	It's very important to them to show their abilities. They want people to admire what they do.
	PVQ_AC2	Being very successful is important to them. They hope people will recognise their achievements.

Hedonism	PVQ_HE1	Having a good time is important to them. They like to "spoil" themselves.
	PVQ_HE2	They seek every chance to have fun. It is important to them to do things that give them pleasure
Stimulation	PVQ_ST1	They like surprises and are always looking for new things to do. They think it is important to do lots of different things in life.
	PVQ_ST2	They look for adventures and like to take risks. They want to have an exciting life.
Self-direction	PVQ_SD1	Thinking up new ideas and being creative is important to them. They like to do things in their own original way.
	PVQ_SD2	It is important to them to make their own decisions about what they do. They like to be free and not depend on others.

How can we measure the value structure?

The analysis as well as the representation of the children's value structure was carried out by means of multidimensional scaling (MDS). According to Borg (2010), MDS contains different procedures with which objects are represented as points in a coordinate system in a two- or three-dimensional space. Based on a pairwise correlation matrix, MDS refracts the ordinal information in a two-dimensional space and plots the data points along the two dimensions on the corresponding coordinate (Borg & Staufenbiel, 2007). According to Borg and Staufenbiel (2007, p. 160), the graphical representation of the correlations between items in the form of points allows "the structure of the intercorrelations to be explored by eye" and thus makes it easier to grasp correlations.

Similar to the measurement of the children's value structure, we analysed the structure of the value-related educational goals with use of MDS.

How are explicit and implicit values taught in primary schools?

Apart from the main role of helping children to learn, a teacher has a moral commitment to further equip their students with democratic values of citizenship, attitudes and beliefs and promote a classroom environment of mutual respect, care, honesty and trust. Thus teachers are not only delivering classroom lessons, but also play a critical role in the development of children's values. There is limited evidence on how values are transmitted between teachers and their students. Questions arise on what methods - explicit or implicit- the teachers employ to share values with their students. In an ethical classroom, teaching, modelling and reinforcement can foster the value transmission (Boekaerts et al, 2006). Understanding the

methods and processes of value transmission in the classroom not only provides valuable insight into how school shapes children's value but also how children learn in general.

According to Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems model (1979), child development is a complex system of interacting relationships affected by multiple levels. This research into teacher-child value transmission (Jones, 2022) applies Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems model to investigate how proximal processes (micro-system) in the classroom (between the teacher students and among students) influence value transmission. Furthermore, the study examines the interaction between the micro- and meso-system, in particular how school climate may affect value transmission and how home, school and the wider community interact with each other (Döring et al, 2021), and how educational policies and planning (national curriculum) shape the value transmission on a macro level.

4. Selection of initial analyses of the sample

4.1 Value structure of the children

The MDS of the UK sample shows that children at primary school age already have a value structure that corresponds to Schwartz's (1992) value model (figure 1). This means that both the basic values hedonism, self-direction and stimulation versus the three values of tradition, conformity and security, as well as the universalism and benevolence vis-à-vis the basic values power and achievement are at the correct region. The MDS of the value structure for Year 2 and Year 3 students is displayed in figures 2 and 3 respectively. The value structure for both year groups however, is still quite close to the centre with the values for self-transcendence and conservation being particularly clustered together.

Looking at differences between the year groups, it seems that the values that belong together (with the same colour) mostly get closer together. This means their correlation gets stronger. The distance from one item to the other shows the correlation between two items and serves as a measure of similarity.

The correlation is stronger the closer the points are to each other in space. Conclusions from the two year groups need to be taken cautiously as they only present a snapshot in time. It is unclear whether the fit of the children's value structure gets better with maturity, or if the results reflect cohort effects.

In both structures, items that belong to the same value types are in neighbouring regions and can be divided into the four higher order values.

Taking a closer look at the MDS, one can see two outliers (SE1, BE1). These may be explained by the very heterogeneous cognitive and linguistic development of the children at this young age. It seems that not all children at this age are able to fulfil the cognitive and developmental requirements of the PBVS-C.

Figure 2 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (Year 2)

Figure 3 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (Year 3)

4.2 Values priorities of children

The results on the value priorities in Table 10 provide information of which values are important to the children, and which are not so important for Year 2 and Year 3 students. The children's value priorities show that for the children as a whole as well as broken down into age groups, benevolence is the most important value. Promoting the well-being of the people close to them is at the top. At the lowest end of the hierarchy of values for the children is the value power. Social status, prestige and authority seem to be the least important for the children. In Year 3, security is as important as benevolence, and in Year 2 it is a very close second. Although the most important as well as the least important basic value of the children are the same, age differences can be seen (e.g., tradition or conformity), with Year 2 students prioritising tradition (4) over hedonism (5), conformity (6), self-direction (7) and stimulation (8). Year 3 students on the contrary, prioritise hedonism (4) over tradition (5), self-direction (6), stimulation (7) and conformity (8). It may be that older children favour self-enhancement over conservation values. Explanatory approaches for the different prioritisation of values could indicate a maturing and stabilising value structure in older children. However, these data are cross-sectional and only represent a snapshot in time which may not be guaranteed to be representative. Cross-sectional data alone should not be employed to determine cause and effect, but gives pathways for additional hypotheses and assumption. Further research is needed to investigate these patterns in value change in the UK.

Table 10 Value priorities subsumed to value type; by year groups (Year 2 and Year 3)

Variable	combined				Year 2				Year 3			
	N	M	SD	Rank	N	M	SD	Rank	N	M	SD	Rank
UN	536	3.28	.69	3	308	3.30	.68	3	228	3.25	.71	3
BE	536	3.58	.65	1	308	3.58	.63	1	228	3.58	.69	1
TR	536	3.04	.71	5	308	3.08	.73	4	228	2.98	.69	5
CO	536	2.91	.64	7	308	2.94	.66	6	228	2.86	.61	8
SE	536	3.53	.73	2	308	3.49	.76	2	228	3.58	.70	1
PO	536	2.16	.83	10	308	2.21	.85	10	228	2.09	.79	10
AC	536	2.62	.74	9	308	2.63	.75	9	228	2.61	.74	9
HE	536	3.06	.73	4	308	3.00	.74	5	228	3.13	.72	4
ST	536	2.89	.65	8	308	2.85	.65	8	228	2.94	.64	7
SD	536	2.94	.64	6	308	2.92	.61	7	228	2.97	.64	6

The analysis of the four higher-order value types indicates that the total sample and both year groups rank self-transcendence as the most important higher-order value type (table 11). This is not surprising, since humanistic and universalistic basic values are at the top of the value hierarchy. The well-being of their fellow human beings and the protection of nature seem to be the primary concerns for the pupils. Year 2 students give weight to self-transcendence more than Year 3. The higher order value type of self-enhancement, on the other hand, occupies the last place in the value hierarchy for both year groups. It follows that both year groups focus more on social relationships and other people than themselves. Finally, the rankings of self-transcendence and self-enhancement confirm the motivational contrast the two occupy in Schwartz's theory of values (1992, 1994). Both year groups rank conservation values as second and openness to change as third.

Table 11 *Value priorities subsumed to higher order value; by year groups (Year 2 and Year 3)*

Variable	combined				Year 2				Year 3			
	N	M	SD	Rank	N	M	SD	Rank	N	M	SD	Rank
SeTr	536	3.43	.49	1	308	3.44	.49	1	228	3.42	.50	1
Cons	536	3.16	.40	2	308	3.17	.42	2	228	3.13	.37	2
SeEn	536	2.39	.64	4	308	2.42	.65	4	228	2.35	.61	4
OtC	536	2.96	.39	3	308	2.93	.39	3	228	3.02	.40	3

4.3 Structure of teachers' value-related educational goals

The MDS of the teacher sample shows that primary school teachers' value-related educational goals have a structure that corresponds to Schwartz's (1992) value model (figure 1). The MDS of the structure of the value-related educational goals is displayed in figure 4. Investigating the structure, items that belong to a same value are in neighbouring regions and can be divided into the four higher order values, however, the items were still quite close to the centre.

Figure 4 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS

4.4 Priorities of teachers' value-related educational goals

Similar to the children's personal values, teachers' value-related educational goals in the UK follow a typical ranking of values. Interestingly, teachers in Year 2 and Year 3 ranked universalism in first place (which ranked third in the children sample) indicating that they are most likely to promote universalism-oriented values. As expected, the value power took last place. A similar effect can be observed in the higher order value priorities for teachers' value-related educational goals (table 14). Supporting the findings from the children data, teachers favoured self-transcendent higher order values most and self-enhancement higher order values least. But because of the cross-sectional nature of the data it is unclear whether these educational goals influence children's personal values and to what extent. Further longitudinal follow-up research could illuminate the contrasting relationship between teachers educational goals and children's personal values in the UK. Similar to the children, teachers want their students to focus more on social relationships and other people than themselves.

Table 13 *Value-related educational goals - subsumed to value type; combined (female/male and Year 2 / Year 3)*

Variable	combined			
	N	M	SD	Rank
UN	37	5.35	1.07	1
BE	37	5.21	1.00	2
TR	37	4.33	1.15	7
CO	37	4.28	1.21	8
SE	37	4.56	1.27	4
PO	37	3.44	.88	10
AC	37	4.36	1.30	6
HE	37	4.13	1.20	9
ST	37	4.51	1.11	5
SD	37	4.96	.69	3

Table 14 *Value-related educational goals subsumed to higher order value; combined (female/male and Year 2 /Year 3)*

Variable	combined			
	N	M	SD	Rank
SeTr	37	5.28	.90	1
Cons	37	4.39	.95	3
SeEn	37	3.90	.88	4
OtC	37	4.53	.86	2

5. Selection of initial analyses of the sample

What are the values that are important to the teachers and how do they transmit these to their pupils?

Given the limited empirical evidence assessing the processes at play in transmitting values within the school setting, this qualitative study (Jones, 2022) aims to fill a gap in the literature by providing insights from teachers' own experiences. Whereas previous studies focused on a values education, the teachers interviewed in this study suggest that values are transmitted more extensively, across all areas of the curriculum, albeit not always consciously. In particular, teachers felt that their own values, which might include values of integrity, honesty, inclusion, having good relationships and treating others how you wish to be treated, encompass all aspects of their persona – as a parent, partner, friend and teacher. As a result, teachers believe that they cannot help but instil their own values to their pupils, and perhaps more importantly, see it as their moral duty to do so. However, at the same time they recognise that pupils' values are also influenced by their home and peers. Specifically, by showing tolerance to other people's differences, teachers share values of universalism. Achievement values could be shown in terms of teacher encouragement to work hard for what you want. By building positive relationships in the classroom filled with mutual respect, teachers use a range of methods to transmit values including, through discussion, modelling, role play, priming, school visits and by providing time for reflection.

What methods and contexts are used by the teachers to instil values ?

Using thematic analysis, 7 main themes emerged regarding the mechanisms and contexts in which values are transmitted between teachers and students: 1) Mechanisms of value

transmission; 2) Implicit vs explicit instruction of values; 3) Values that are most difficult to teach; 4) Value transmission in taught lessons; 5) The role of collective worship and cultural days; 6) Opportunities for value transmission in the wider school environment; 7) School ethos and the impact of the Head teacher.

Teachers interviewed felt that some values need to be taught explicitly and others are taught more implicitly, almost subconsciously. In Nursery and KS1 (Years 1 and 2), where children start to learn how to get along with others through sharing, listening and being responsible, teachers reinforce conformity values so that children can follow instructions, such as sitting on the carpet, putting your hand up and lining up. These explicit values are usually easier to grasp, particularly as over time, they may form habits. Even in KS2 (Year 3 to Year 6), some values need to be taught explicitly, for instance being reflective, resilient and how to develop independent learning. In contrast, implicit values, which are often more abstract, require more automatic processing and are often more challenging to teach. Because they relate to issues which are not always talked about every day, children may find them less easy to apply in their everyday life. These might include universal values or values linked to empathy and thinking of the consequences of your own actions on others. Even self-direction values can present challenges. Consequently, teachers felt that values should be taught both explicitly and implicitly with lots of priming, modelling and using real-life examples wherever possible, giving the children the opportunity to recognise the value and assess how to respond next time. Moreover, values need to be repeated regularly in order to be assimilated – a standalone lesson is not enough for children to apply some values, particularly if they are more abstract.

Furthermore, teachers reported that values were taught through a variety of ways in primary school settings: standalone PSHE lessons, ad hoc sessions in response to occurrences in the playground or in the classroom, through assemblies and through academic subjects. Without thinking about it, values can filter through all areas of the curriculum. By giving concrete examples, children can contextualise the value that the teachers are trying to instil and then apply it later. Giving children time for discussion and reflection is also important as it is not always easy for children to put into practice what they have learnt immediately. Furthermore, the school ethos and the leadership or vision of the head teacher play a significant role in how values are perceived and shaped in the school setting. Parents may select the school which conforms most appropriately to their own values which means that children's values usually reflect those of the school. Similarly, teachers emphasised that working cohesively and collaboratively to promote whole school values awards greater success in the implementation and transmission of those values.

6. Follow-up and thank you

Follow-up more specific and novel analyses will be published in relevant journals and presented at conferences in the next phase of the project (September 2022 - August 2024).

A very special thanks to all the participating schools for inviting the team to work with them. A big thanks to all the children (and parents) and teachers who participated in this research for your warm welcome and hard work. Most importantly, I would like to say thank you to our excellent research team for their your time and effort that made this research study possible.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact the Valise team via email valise@unibas.ch or Twitter [@VALISEproject](https://twitter.com/VALISEproject), or visit our website (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-formation-in-school/>) for more information on the project as well as the newest publications.

7. Research Output

The list of our research output will be regularly updated on our website (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-formation-in-school/>).

So far, two scientific articles were published (August 2022):

Oeschger, T., Makarova E., & Döring, A. (2022). Values in the School Curriculum from Teachers' Perspective: A mixed-methods Study. *International Journal of Educational Research Open, Volume 3*. doi:10.1016/j.ijedro.2022.100190

Scholz-Kuhn, R., Oeschger, T., Makarova, E., & Döring A. (2021). Wertetransmission in der Schule: Eine Studie zu Werthaltungen von Kindern und Lehrpersonen auf der Primarstufe. *Die Grundschulzeitschrift*.

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